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Operating Welfare
Indicators for shrimp

Advancing Trust
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in European Seafood

The demand for not just high-quality, but also high-welfare seafood is driving the need for tools such as OWIs. Photograph: Aquaculture Stewardship Council.

Operational Welfare Indicators for Shrimp Farming: Current Trends and Future Directions

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The use of Operational Welfare Indicators (OWIs) is becoming increasingly important in aquaculture. These indicators are easily measurable parameters to assess the welfare of farmed fish and crustaceans, addressing a growing demand for ethical and sustainable seafood production. Despite advances in aquaculture practices, the implementation of OWIs in shrimp farming remains limited due to practical and economic constraints. This article provides a brief research overview of the use of OWIs in shrimp farming and examines current practices and challenges in South America and Asia.

Research Overview

Shrimp farming has expanded significantly over the past few decades, becoming an important contributor to the global aquaculture sector. The Global Seafood Alliance estimated that 5.6 million metric tonnes (MMT) of farmed shrimp were produced globally in 2023, *Litopenaeus vannamei* (Pacific White shrimp/Whiteleg shrimp) being the dominating species. Research into shrimp welfare has historically fallen behind that of fish species, largely due to the common misconception that invertebrates experience less complex suffering. While scientific consensus on shrimp sentience and their ability to suffer remains inconclusive due to limited research, a lack of definitive evidence does not equate to a lack of sentience. This view is shaping regulations like the UK's Animal Welfare (Sentience) Act 2022, which recognizes decapod crustaceans as sentient, alongside similar laws in Australia, New Zealand, Norway, and Switzerland.

Recent studies suggest that shrimp exhibit a stress response, and behavioural changes under adverse conditions, emphasising the need for welfare assessment tools like OWIs. While OWIs are essential for maintaining shrimp health and productivity, their application as a welfare tool is still in its infancy compared to their use in fish farming.

Current Practices of OWIs around the World

Ecuador and Brazil are establishing themselves as leaders in shrimp farming, particularly for *L. vannamei*. In Ecuador, producers often operate semi-intensive and intensive systems, emphasising high yields and biosecurity. While water quality management and disease monitoring are routine, assessment of shrimp welfare remains limited. Efforts are more focused on optimising production efficiency and addressing environmental sustainability.

Ecuador has gained recognition for innovations in low-density shrimp farming, which indirectly supports welfare by reducing stress and disease risks. However, the explicit use of welfare indicators, beyond those related to production metrics, is uncommon. Local organisations and academic institutions are beginning to explore OWI frameworks, but adoption is uneven across the sector.

Asia is the largest producer of farmed shrimp, contributing more than 80% of the world's supply, (Certifications and Ratings Collaboration). Farming systems range from traditional extensive practices to high-tech, intensive operations. As observed in Ecuador, many traditional farms are encouraged to use small scale and semi/low intensity approach - due to customer appeal in part, but mainly to minimise disease outbreaks. While this approach likely improves welfare, it is not usually measured. In intensive systems, water quality parameters such as pH, salinity, and dissolved oxygen are meticulously controlled. However, welfare considerations beyond these basic operational metrics are often overlooked.

Thailand has embraced technological advancements like automated feeding systems and real-time water quality monitoring, which align with some OWI principles. Yet, welfare specific indicators are rarely incorporated into routine practices. In many cases, the lack of standardised welfare protocols limits progress and risks stocks, despite growing interest from international markets demanding higher welfare standards.

The dominance of Asia and South America in shrimp farming is largely due to their natural climate, economic advantages, industry expertise, and government support. These

Asia is the biggest producer of farmed shrimp and houses some of the largest farms in the world. Photograph: Vietnam Fisheries Magazine.

The demand for not just high-quality, but also high-welfare seafood is driving the need for tools such as OWIs. Photograph: FloGro via The Fish Site.

factors allow for high production levels at competitive prices, making them the world's leading shrimp suppliers.

Constraints to the Use of OWIs

Economic and Resource Barriers

The primary constraint to implementing OWIs in shrimp farming is cost. Developing, validating, and applying OWIs often requires training and ongoing monitoring. For small-scale farmers—who represent a significant portion of shrimp producers in Asia and South America—the costs associated are hard to justify. Many farmers prioritise immediate productivity and survival rates over long-term welfare considerations, especially in regions where profit margins are slim.

Lack of Standardisation

Unlike vertebrate aquaculture, shrimp farming lacks universally accepted welfare guidelines. This absence of standardisation makes it challenging for producers to adopt OWIs consistently. Variability in farming systems, species, and local environmental conditions further complicates the development of applicable and meaningful indicators.

Limited Awareness and Research

Awareness of shrimp welfare as a critical component of sustainable aquaculture remains low among stakeholders. While research into OWIs is growing, it remains insufficient in providing comprehensive frameworks for the diverse conditions under which shrimp are farmed globally. Cultural perceptions of shrimp as being less sentient than vertebrates also contributes to the slow uptake of more welfare-focused practices in aquaculture.

Market and Regulatory Pressures

Consumer demand for ethically produced seafood is rising, particularly in Europe and North America. Notably, several UK-based supermarket chains including Waitrose, Tesco and Marks & Spencer, have recently announced a commitment to improving shrimp welfare through measures including electrical stunning prior to slaughter. This move follows

increasing scrutiny of the treatment of farmed shrimp and aligns with growing consumer expectations for higher welfare standards. Despite these pressures, producers often lack the regulatory mechanisms to enforce welfare standards for imported shrimp. Producers in exporting countries are unlikely to adopt OWIs without clear economic incentives or regulatory mandates. Additionally, the fragmented nature of the global shrimp supply chain makes traceability and accountability for welfare challenging.

Opinions from Experts

To gain deeper insights into the importance and challenges of implementing OWIs in shrimp farming, I spoke with several experts in the field: Kathrin Steinberg, Maria Filipa Castanheira and Marianne Green at the Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC) (<https://asc-aqua.org/>), Marco Custódio, aquaculture expert and Project Manager at Earthworm Foundation France (<https://earthworm.org/>), and Justine Deletre, Program Officer at Mr. Goodfish (<https://www.mrgoodfish.com/en/>).

Why Are OWIs Critical for Shrimp Farming?

The experts interviewed agree that OWIs are essential for monitoring shrimp welfare and ensuring quick intervention when stress or disease is detected. By providing real-time assessments, these indicators allow farmers to adjust conditions promptly, improving both welfare and productivity. Customized OWIs, developed based on past farm performance, veterinary guidance, and research benchmarks, make implementation practical across different farming systems. Additionally, OWIs contribute to sustainability goals by reducing disease outbreaks and enhancing farm management strategies.

According to the team at the ASC, the flexibility of OWIs makes them invaluable for aligning shrimp farming with sustainability efforts, particularly under the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 14 and SDG 12). Custódio emphasized their role in providing critical data for farm management, improving decision-making, and minimizing environmental impact. Deletre highlighted their benefits in ensuring producers can track shrimp health in real-time, allowing immediate adjustments to farming conditions.

Beyond farm-level benefits, OWIs play a crucial role in meeting consumer demand for ethical seafood. As awareness of animal welfare grows, transparent monitoring systems provide credibility to certification schemes and strengthen consumer confidence in sustainably farmed shrimp.

Current Gaps and Challenges in OWI Implementation

Despite their potential, OWIs are not yet widely adopted across the shrimp farming industry. Many farms focus primarily on water quality and survival rates, often neglecting more nuanced welfare indicators such as behavioural changes or physiological stress markers. Expanding OWI monitoring to include activity levels and biochemical stress indicators, such as Crustacean Hyperglycaemic Hormone (CHH; an analog to cortisol), would provide a more holistic assessment of shrimp well-being.

Asia is the biggest producer of farmed shrimp and houses some of the largest farms in the world. Photograph: Lim Shrimp Organisation via The Fish Site.

While farmed shrimp is a large contributor to the global aquaculture market, welfare monitoring falls behind that of farmed fish. Photograph: Isla Monaghan, Swansea University.

Economic barriers remain a significant challenge. Small-scale farmers, who form a large part of global shrimp production, often lack the financial resources to invest in welfare monitoring technologies. Even for larger farms, incentives to adopt OWIs are limited without stronger market demand or regulatory requirements. Deletre pointed out that a lack of standardisation across the industry makes OWI implementation inconsistent. Custódio stressed that many farms still operate without clear welfare benchmarks, preventing uniform adoption.

Limited training and research investment further complicates implementation. Many farmers are unfamiliar with how to integrate welfare indicators into their management strategies, and funding for shrimp welfare studies remains scarce compared to research on vertebrate aquaculture. ASC noted that without greater investment in research and training, the industry will struggle to apply OWIs effectively at a meaningful scale.

Consumer Awareness and Market Influence

Consumer perception of farmed shrimp and its welfare implications plays a crucial role in the adoption of OWIs. Unlike land-based livestock, shrimp farming is less visible to the public, making welfare concerns less prominent. However, increased scrutiny from NGOs and retailer-led campaigns against harmful practices, such as eyestalk ablation, are slowly pushing shrimp welfare into mainstream discussions.

While some certification schemes include welfare components, general awareness remains low. Transparent

labelling and clearer welfare certifications could drive greater demand for responsibly farmed shrimp, encouraging more producers to adopt OWIs. Custódio mentioned that current market dynamics often prioritize cost and efficiency over welfare, making it difficult for welfare-focused initiatives to gain traction. Delettre emphasized that increased consumer education is necessary to shift purchasing habits in favour of welfare-certified seafood.

The Path Forward: Recommendations for OWI Integration

To enhance the adoption of OWIs, industry leaders, regulatory bodies, and certification schemes must collaborate on standardised welfare benchmarks tailored to different farming systems. Programs like ASC's Improver Programme already provide guidance for farms looking to improve welfare standards, but broader industry participation is needed.

Financial incentives, such as subsidies or premium pricing for welfare-certified shrimp, have the potential to further encourage farmers to integrate OWIs into their operations. Collaboration between research institutions, industry stakeholders, and policymakers are considered crucial in developing scalable welfare solutions that balance cost-effectiveness with ethical responsibility.

With the recent global development of large-scale RAS (Recirculating Aquaculture Systems) for shrimp farming, it is incredibly important to develop easy, cost effective and less invasive measures of monitoring welfare. Investment in scientific research is also necessary to refine OWI methodologies and establish clear, practical monitoring systems. By increasing transparency in farming practices, the industry can strengthen consumer trust and market engagement, further driving welfare improvements.

Ultimately, integrating OWIs into shrimp farming is both a welfare priority and a long-term business strategy. Proactively addressing welfare concerns can enhance shrimp survival rates, improve farm efficiency, and align production with evolving consumer expectations for sustainable and ethical seafood.

Development and validation of OWIs for shrimp at CSAR, Swansea University

The Centre for Sustainable Aquatic Research (CSAR) at Swansea University; (<https://www.swansea.ac.uk/bioscience/facilities/csar/>) is actively working to advance shrimp welfare through the development of comprehensive Operational Welfare Indicators. With increasing recognition of the importance of shrimp welfare in aquaculture, CSAR aims to create a scientifically grounded and practical welfare assessment framework that can be applied across different farming systems. This research is part of the IGNITION project; (<https://ignition-project.eu/>), which aims to gather new knowledge in animal welfare in the context of climate change, as well as assessing and developing new strategies to improve animal health through non-invasive tools. Our work for the IGNITION project is focusing on the response of the white leg shrimp to different stressors, environmental changes and on the development of rapid OWIs that can be used by farmers.

The OWI scoring system is being tested extensively by several researchers at CSAR to achieve accuracy and ease of use. Photograph: Isla Monaghan, Swansea University.

In particular, CSAR's research focuses on designing a reliable welfare scoring system that provides shrimp farmers with accessible tools to monitor and enhance welfare conditions effectively. The project involves identifying key physical indicators of shrimp health, refining scoring criteria, and ensuring that the system is applicable to commercial farming environments. This initiative aligns with global efforts to promote sustainable aquaculture and improve the welfare of farmed crustaceans.

One of the primary objectives at CSAR is to establish OWIs that are both practical and scientifically validated. Many existing welfare measures focus on water quality and productivity, but CSAR's approach goes beyond these basic parameters. The team is working on a scoring system that evaluates multiple welfare indicators, allowing for early detection of health concerns and environmental stressors. This system is designed to be user-friendly, enabling shrimp farmers to implement welfare monitoring without requiring extensive scientific expertise. CSAR's efforts are also directed at ensuring the scalability of OWIs. The indicators developed must be applicable to various shrimp farming systems, including extensive, semi-intensive, and intensive production models. The OWI scoring system is currently being tested by CSAR researchers to assess repeatability, accuracy and ease of use. By considering different farming environments, the research aims to create a welfare assessment method that is adaptable and effective across a range of production settings.

Research carried out at CSAR also explores how different environmental stressors, such as temperature fluctuations and salinity changes, may impact shrimp welfare. By monitoring behavioural and physiological responses to these conditions, the team is developing OWIs that can serve as early warning signals of welfare. This work is particularly important as climate change continues to affect shrimp farming regions, making adaptable welfare monitoring tools increasingly necessary.

Additionally, the project is evaluating non-invasive methods of monitoring welfare including machine vision and behavioural tracking. These approaches align with industry

CSAR is committed to supporting the IGNITION Project's mission to improve animal health and welfare, resilience and sustainability. Photograph: Isla Monaghan, Swansea University.

needs for efficient and scalable welfare monitoring solutions that do not compromise production efficiency. By creating welfare indicators that can be integrated into aquaculture systems, CSAR is supporting IGNITION's mission to improve sustainability, animal health, and resilience to environmental stressors. As part of this collaboration, CSAR is helping to set new welfare benchmarks that can be adopted globally to ensure ethical and responsible shrimp farming.

A key component of this work is industry collaboration. Only through engagement with shrimp farmers, researchers, and other stakeholders can OWIs be refined, ensuring their relevance to real-world aquaculture operations. This collaborative approach helps bridge the gap between academic research and industry practice, facilitating the practical application of welfare assessment tools.

Potential Impact and Future Directions

The development of OWIs at CSAR has the potential to significantly enhance shrimp welfare management. By providing a standardized and objective method for welfare assessment, the project aims to support the adoption of higher welfare standards across the shrimp farming sector. As consumer awareness and regulatory pressures continue to grow, having a scientifically validated welfare assessment system in place will be crucial for farmers aiming to meet evolving sustainability and ethical standards.

Moreover, the integration of OWIs into shrimp farming practices could lead to broader benefits beyond welfare improvements. Enhanced welfare conditions have been linked to higher survival rates, improved growth performance, and reduced disease outbreaks—factors that contribute to both economic viability and environmental sustainability. By reducing stress-related mortality and optimizing farming conditions, OWIs can support a more efficient and responsible shrimp aquaculture industry.

Looking ahead, CSAR's research will continue to evolve, incorporating emerging scientific insights and industry feedback. The goal is to develop a robust welfare monitoring framework that can be widely adopted by shrimp farmers worldwide. This initiative underscores the importance of

advancing shrimp welfare science and integrating welfare-focused practices into mainstream aquaculture.

Closing remarks

The implementation of OWIs in shrimp farming represents a significant step toward improving welfare standards in aquaculture. Research has highlighted the necessity of welfare monitoring, and expert opinions emphasize the potential benefits of OWIs for both sustainability and productivity. However, challenges such as economic constraints, lack of standardization, and limited awareness continue to hinder widespread adoption.

The efforts at CSAR, Swansea University, mark an important advancement in addressing these challenges. Our approach, which prioritises real-world applicability and industry collaboration, ensures that welfare monitoring can be integrated into diverse farming systems.

Moving forward, the success of OWIs will depend on continued research, stakeholder engagement, and regulatory support. As consumer demand for ethically produced seafood increases, shrimp farming operations will need to adopt welfare-focused strategies to remain competitive. The development and refinement of OWIs will not only enhance shrimp welfare but also contribute to the long-term sustainability and economic viability of the industry.

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